

Organisational Leadership and Style Adopting in the Hospitality Industry

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History

Published Online: 30 July 2018

Keywords

Organization, Hospitality Industry, organisational culture, Leadership, Transformational Leadership

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ABSTRACT

The importance of organisational leadership has been the fundamental step to the success of firms, even for the global and dynamic industries. By and large, firms within the hospitality industry understanding this concept have yet to put this in practice globally as well as in the local markets for meeting the success especially those firms that are in the process of striving to become industry leaders. The hospitality industry is complex, dynamic, and global thus it becomes challenging for the firms of this industry to sustain the continuous development and competitiveness that's happening continuously. This article reviews the literature concerning the organisational leadership adopting in the hospitality industry. Comprehensive search was made and reviewed the literature from which were selected, organized, and analysed accordingly. This review paper delves into the concept of organisational leadership and its characteristics, while highlighting the steps taken by few such firms in the hospitality industry which will help in identifying and setting the standards of organisational leadership globally. The leadership perspective is discussed in the context of the Indian hospitality industry to highlight how the concept can be applied to developing markets for meeting the success to become pioneers of the industry.

1. Introduction

Organization is nothing but, it's a process of integrating and coordinating the efforts of men and material for the accomplishment of set of objectives. An organization is a process that leads recognition and classification of work to be performed which for accessibility sake should be objectively grouped and defined. Then the work should be assigned to individuals according to their aptitude, technical knowledge, skill and efficiency. The formal organization is basically goal-oriented entity that exist to accurate the efforts of individuals and it refers to the structure of jobs and positions with clearly defined functions, responsibilities and authorities. An organization can be the primary source of an individual's social identity (Hogg&Terry, 2001). Organizational identification has important implications for both employees and employers. Identification with an organization helps employees to enhance collective self-esteem (Ashforth et al., 2008). As mentioned by Dutton, Dukerich, and Harquail (1994), when identification is strong, employees include the unique, central, and persistent attributes that define the organization into their self-concepts and the differences between their personal and organizational identities become blurred. Subsequently, employees feel the successes and failures of their organization as their own, and they engage in behaviours that help the organization to achieve its goals and objectives. Organizational goals and objectives provide the foundation for measurement. They are the outcome statements that define what an organization is trying to accomplish, both programmatically and organizationally. These goals are usually a collection of related programs, a reflection of major actions of the organization, and provide rallying points for managers/leaders. In order to accomplish these goals and objectives of the organization an efficient leading and managing role has to be created in the organization, one who leads the entire management or various teams within the organization with his/her unique style that makes everyone to walk towards

reaching their organizational objectives. The leadership offered within the organization has been targeted as a potential area for enhancing organizational performance (Overall, 2015). The definition of leadership indicates that this process involves the ability of one individual to motivate and influence others. Ideally motivation and influence occur in a manner that is positive and respectful, contributing to the achievement of specific goals (de Oliveira Rodriguez & Ferreira, 2015). Trait, behavioral, situational, transactional, and transformational leadership styles are just a few of the theories that have been proposed to evaluate the rudiments of leader behavior and the basis for motivation and influence (Ghasabeh et al., 2015). The core functions of an organization are to meet its objectives, adapt to its environment, and to maintain the stability of its system (Argyris, 1964). As mentioned by Katz & Kahn, (1978) leadership involves in understanding the systemic nature of the organization, and producing and assimilating its distinct functions to compensate for deficiencies in the system and changes in the environment. Furthermore, it was stated by Vaill (1978) that leaders must be "experts in the techniques of the system's basic activity" in combining human and technological resources to reach the organization's objectives. These aspects of leadership are parallel functions to those of other important leadership actions. Well said by Waldman & Yammarino, (1999) that these leader actions are essential for effective system design, which in turn provides the conditions for effective worker performance. By knowing the dynamic and systemic nature of the organization, the leader is able to set reasonable but attainable strategic objectives, structure tasks appropriately, and provide necessary guidelines for task completion.

2. The Hospitality Industry

It has been mistakenly argued that the insight of the hospitality industry as dull and low-skilled has troubled the recruitment efforts of many organisations and restricted the pool

of labour to young people, women and those who are marginalised in society (see Lucas and Bailey, 1993; Purcell, 1993; Lee-Ross and Johns, 1995). These and other issues have led researchers to conclude that the industry is not conducive to the practice of HRM (for example, Price, 1994). However, fascinatingly, it has equally been suggested that one way in which executives have attempted to minimise the impact of these problems is through the management of organisational culture. In an extensive review of research into HR issues in the hospitality industry, Guerrier and Deery (1998: 149) conclude that there is a relative dearth of studies into organisational culture in the sector. Those that appear to focus on organisational culture have been generally directed to two broad issues. First, a number of studies have examined the links between organisational culture and performance in the industry and, as such, follow what could be called an optimistic agenda. Secondly, researchers have noted the links between Emmanuel Ogbonna and Lloyd C. Harris organisational culture and other variables that may have a direct or indirect relationship with performance. These two streams of studies are discussed below.

Wilkins and Patterson (1985) say that there are a number of cultural issues that could impede the efficiency of many hospitality organisations. This theme has been taken up by other commentators. For example, Glover (1987) observes that management intransigence towards culture in the industry could result in ineffectiveness, a finding that mirrors the recent suggestion of Kemp and Dwyer (2001) that developing a strong culture can enhance organisational effectiveness. Further, Tidball (1988) argues that there is a direct link between culture and company profitability. However, the most compelling exposition of the connection between organisational culture and performance in the hospitality industry is provided by LeBlanc and Mills (1995), who argue that a strong organisational culture is a pre requisite to organisational improvement and performance in the sector. They identify a range of factors which they urge executives to control in order to develop positive organisational cultures. These include formal organisational structures, physical surroundings and a range of emotion-influencing factors.

While a number of studies have been supportive of a direct culture and performance link, other examinations of organisational culture in the hospitality industry are less deterministic about this. Instead, they focus on identifying the variables that could facilitate or impinge on the culture creation process. Thus, Penzer (1990) focuses on the organisational culture consequences of low pay, a frequently identified problem in the industry, arguing that one way of reducing its negative impact is to encourage a greater sense of employee identification with the company through the creation of a strong organisational culture.

Similarly, other contributions have examined the impact of high turnover on the culture management process in the industry. Notably, Iverson and Deery (1997) provide an empirical evaluation of turnover within the hospitality industry and note that high turnover rates may have a range of negative consequences for organisational culture in the industry. This view is supported by other studies which provide managers with

recipes for reducing turnover through various forms of cultural intervention (see Lockwood and Guerrier, 1989; Woods, 1989; Woods and McCauley, 1989). Insights have also been forwarded by studies into the organisational culture consequence of various types of organisational climate and burnout (see Vallen, 1993).

However, it is arguable that the most comprehensive discussions of organisational culture in the industry are supplied by Brownell (1990), Woods (1991) and Watson and D'Annunzio - Green (1996). Brownell (1990) provides an analysis of organisational change through the application of theories of culture and organisational symbolism. She concludes that managers need to develop greater levels of sophistication in understanding organisational symbolism and culture in order that they may be better able to guide their organisations through planned culture change. In contrast, Woods (1991) provides a clarification of some of the constructs that underpin the concept of organisational culture, and supplies managers with guidance on how to uncover the culture of their organisations.

However, it is the work of Watson and D'Annunzio-Green (1996) that provides detailed insights into the management of organisational culture change in the hospitality industry. In a study of two large hotels, they provide an assessment of the role of HRM in facilitating cultural change and argue that, while HR policies were implemented by both hotels, HRM was not considered central to the culture change process.

Overall, the review of the literature on organisational culture points to a certain level of indeterminacy on the issue of its management. Although some academic researchers are either 'optimistic' or 'realistic' about the prospects of planned cultural intervention in organisations, it appears that much scholarly opinion is centred on the view that culture is firmly embedded in the whole notion of organisation and that it cannot be subjected to any form of systematic and conscious management action with predictable outcomes (see, for example, Anthony, 1990; Martin, 1992; Ogbonna, 1993; Willmott, 1993; Legge, 1994; Rowlinson and Procter, 1999). An examination of the literature on the hospitality industry finds some support for the management of organisational culture.

3. Leadership

Leadership can be defined as the ability of an individual to influence, motivate, and enable others to contribute towards the effectiveness and success of the organizations of which they are members (House, 2004). Organisationally, leadership is expected to directly impact the effectiveness of costs, revenue generation, service, market value, motivation, and sustainability and involves directing, guiding, and supporting employees in order to accomplish their task achievement (Smid & Van der Woude, 2005). Leadership is a competency because it can be trained and developed.

Organisational leadership is an essential ingredient in the success of firms, even more so for industries that are complex, global and dynamic, such as the hospitality industry (Chathoth and Olsen, 2002). In addition to the generic characteristics of management, hospitality managers have different demands and expectations on them, whereby, unlike perhaps a manufacturing

environment, they are concurrently managing both staff performance and guest expectations. Worsfold, (1989a) note that hotel managers, in general, are reasonably autonomous, have low levels of anxiety and have a higher profile in their local business community- as well as having a greater requirement for assertiveness, independence and mental stamina (Worsfold, 1989b).

Today more than ever, hospitality industry has undergone major changes over the last few years (Hartley - Leonard, 1993). For the dynamic change that has taken place there is a need for the dynamic change-oriented leader to handle the new challenges. Thus hospitality executives and managers are faced with significant challenges that require extraordinary insight and skill. Continuous and dynamic change has replaced years of a somewhat predictable and stable operating environment. Immense competition, a declining world economy, over-building, and an increasingly diverse work force are just a few of the many challenges that currently vex the industry (Dobyns and Crawford-Mason, 1991). The cumulative effects of these uncertain and turbulent conditions place great demands on the leadership ability of hospitality executives and managers. In order to effectively cope with these conditions, hospitality leaders may be required to adopt a change-oriented or transformational style of leadership.

4. Transformational Leadership

Today, there has been growing interest and development in the area of transformational leadership. Indeed in the recent times several research studies and articles have been mentioning about the transformational leadership and its strengths. The purpose of this study is to increase our appreciative of the process of transformational leadership and its importance for the hospitality industry. Transformational leadership was first defined by Burns (1978) who proposed leadership process in two ways, which occurs either in transactional or transformational forms. Transactional leadership is based on bureaucratic authority and legitimacy which is associated with one's position within the organization. Transactional leaders lay emphasis on the elucidation of tasks, work standards, and outcomes. In detail a transactional leader is likely to focus on task completion and employee obedience, and these leaders bank on quite heavily on organizational rewards and punishments to influence employee performance.

In recent years, transformational leadership has become a well-known topic in psychology, management, sociology, and political science (Atwater & Yammarino, 1992; Avolio & Bass, 1988; Bass, 1985, 1990; Bass & Avolio, 1989; Bass, Waldman, Avolio, & Bebb, 1987; Bradley, 1987; Burns, 1978; Conger & Kanungo, 1988; Hater & Bass, 1988; House, 1977; Howell & Frost, 1989; Kuhnert & Lewis, 1987; Waldman, Bass, & Einstein, 1987; Yammarino & Bass, 1990). Fundamental principles of transformational leadership appear in the work of Max Weber (1963) on charismatic leadership and Downton (1973) on rebel leadership. But Burns (1978) was the first scholar to specify the distinction between transactional leaders who attempt to satisfy the current needs of followers by focusing attention on exchanges and transformational leaders who attempt to raise the needs of followers and promote dramatic changes of individuals, groups, and organizations.

In contrast, at the extreme end of activity by leaders, even more active than contingent reinforcement (transactional) leadership, is the paradigm of leadership proposed by Burns (1978) and House (1977) and expanded on by Bass (1985, 1990). Superior leadership performance, transformational leadership, is seen when leaders broaden and elevate the interests of their subordinates, when they generate awareness and acceptance among subordinates of the purposes and mission of the group, and when they move their subordinates to go beyond their own self-interests for the good of the group (Burns, 1978). Transformational leaders motivate subordinates to do more than originally expected. They raise the consciousness of subordinates about the importance and value of designated outcomes and ways of reaching them and, in turn, get subordinates to transcend their own immediate self-interests for the sake of the mission and vision of the organization. Subordinates' confidence levels are raised and their needs are expanded. The heightened level of motivation is linked to three conceptual and empirically derived factors of transformational leadership (Bass, 1985, 1990; Avolio & Bass, 1988; Bass & Avolio, 1989; Hater & Bass, 1988). First, transformational leaders are more charismatic and inspiring in the eyes of their subordinates. Charismatic leaders have great referent power and influence, inspire loyalty to the organization, command respect, and have an ability to see what is important (vision) (House, 1977). Charisma and inspiration provide subordinates with a mission and energize their responses. Subordinates want to identify with these leaders, develop intense feelings about them, and have a high degree of trust and confidence in them. Charismatic leaders excite, arouse, and inspire their subordinates (House, 1977). Charismatic and inspirational qualities have been observed at all levels of organizations (Bass, 1985, 1990; Bass & Avolio, 1989). A second component of transformational leadership is individualized consideration. Although a leader's charisma may attract subordinates to the mission or vision, the leader's use of individualized consideration also significantly contributes to subordinates achieving their fullest potential. The leader pays attention to individual differences in subordinates' needs for growth and development. The leader sets examples and assigns tasks on an individual basis not only to satisfy the immediate needs of subordinates, but also to elevate subordinates' needs and abilities to higher levels. Individualized consideration is, in part, coaching and mentoring and a method of communicating timely information to subordinates. It provides for continuous follow-up and feedback and, perhaps more importantly, links an individual's current needs to the organization's mission and elevates those needs when it is appropriate to do so (Bass, 1985, 1990; Bass & Avolio, 1989). A third component of transformational leadership is intellectual stimulation. An intellectually stimulating leader arouses in subordinates an awareness of problems, an awareness of their own thoughts and imagination, and a recognition of their beliefs and values. Intellectual stimulation is seen in subordinates' conceptualization, comprehension, and analysis of problems they face and solutions they generate. It is through intellectual stimulation of subordinates that new methods of accomplishing the organization's mission are explored. Leaders are willing and able to show subordinates new ways of looking at old methods (Bass, 1985, 1990; Bass & Avolio, 1989).

The transformational leadership dimensions of individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation proposed by Bass (1985) may be similar to the higher-order “currencies of exchange” described by Dienesch and Liden (1986). That is, individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation may be shown to subordinates only when the leader receives affect, stimulation, or commitment in return. However, charisma, a third dimension of transformational leadership, may not be exchanged based (Bass, 1985; House, 1977). Charismatic leadership involves the articulation of an inspiring vision, engaging in exemplary acts which subordinates interpret as involving great personal risk and sacrifice, and instilling intense feelings and confidence in subordinates (Bass, 1985, 1990; Conger & Kanungo, 1988; House, 1977). Kuhnert and Lewis (1987) proposed that charismatic leaders have deeply held values that are not used as currencies of exchange. Rather, charismatic leaders are able to influence and inspire followers on the basis of these values.

Researchers have stressed the importance of organizational leadership as being fundamental to the success of firms, even more so for industries that are global and dynamic. The hospitality industry is complex, dynamic, and global; as a result it becomes challenging for the firms of the industry to sustain their competitiveness on a continuous basis. The key to being a leader lies in the firm’s ability to manage change as suggested by Olsen, West and Tse (1998). Given the forces of change that have impact on businesses within the hospitality industry, it is essential to identify firms’ leadership characteristics that help in sustaining competitive advantage in a dynamic global/local environment.

Transformational leaders influence followers’ organizational commitment by encouraging followers to think critically by using novel approaches, involving followers in decision-making processes, inspiring loyalty, while recognizing and appreciating the different needs of each follower to develop his or her personal potential (Avolio, 1999; Bass & Avolio, 1994; Yammarino, Spangler, & Bass, 1993). By encouraging followers to seek new ways to approach problems and challenges, and identifying with followers’ needs, transformational leaders are able to motivate their followers to get more involved in their work, resulting in higher levels of organizational commitment (Walumbwa & Lawler, 2003). This view was supported by prior research that showed organizational commitment was higher for employees whose leaders encouraged participation in decision-making (Jermier & Berkes, 1979; Rhodes & Steers, 1981), emphasized consideration (Bycio, Hackett, & Allen, 1995), and were supportive and concerned for their followers’ development (Allen & Meyer, 1990, 1996). Although transformational leadership has been conceptually and empirically linked to organizational commitment, there has been little empirical research focusing on the processes by which transformational leaders influence followers’ level of organizational commitment (see Bono & Judge, 2003; for exceptions).

The type of change, i.e. transformational change is included by considering mergers and acquisitions (Bellou, 2006). Many prominent authors in this field have found the significant impact of the type of change (Morrison and Robinson, 2000; Rousseau, 1995; Bouckenoghe, 2010). Rousseau (1995) has identified

two types of organizational changes; 1) Transformational change, and 2) Accommodative change. A clear distinction can be made between these two types i.e. transformational changes are revolutionary changes related to change in nature and redefine the psychological contract in actual like layoffs, downsizing, mergers and acquisitions, new policies and procedures etc. On the other hand, accommodative changes are evolutionary adjustments to the current psychological contract framework like working hours, benefit and pay packages, appraisal criteria etc. It is proposed that when changes are introduced to employees’ daily work routine, tasks, roles, or assignments, employees will more likely to adapt new work conditions and make necessary amendments towards his perceived fulfilment of employer obligations which in turn results change in existing psychological contract (Freese, 2007). Therefore, transformational changes are more likely to strongly influence the content of psychological contract fulfilment as compared to accommodative type of organizational change.

NUTSHELL OF THE PAPER: Today, there has been growing interest and development in the area of transformational leadership. Indeed in the recent times several research studies and articles have been mentioning about the transformational leadership and its strengths. The purpose of this study is to increase our appreciative of the process of transformational leadership and its importance for the hospitality industry. This review finds that the researchers have stressed the importance of organizational leadership as being fundamental to the success of firms, even more so for industries that are global and dynamic. In order to effectively cope with these conditions, hospitality leaders may be required to adopt a change-oriented or transformational style of leadership. Transformational changes are more likely to strongly influence the content of psychological contract fulfilment as compared to accommodative type of organizational change.

5. Conclusion

It concludes saying the importance of employee and his or her readiness and willingness for the change management and Organisational Leadership Style adopting in the Hospitality Industry.

The results of this paper review do support the use of transformational leadership to positively influence organizational performance. Even though this model of leadership practice can be important for shaping outcomes for performance, specific elements of the model—intellectual stimulation and individual consideration—appear to play a substantial role in shaping outcomes. With these issues in mind, leaders utilizing transformational leadership should consider these areas for follower development as a means to augment the performance of the organization.

By and large, transformational changes are more likely to strongly influence the content of psychological contract fulfilment as compared to accommodative type of organizational change.

Transformational leaders are more charismatic and inspiring in the eyes of their subordinates. And even the researchers have stressed the importance of organizational leadership as

being fundamental to the success of firms, even more so for industries that is global and dynamic. In order to effectively cope with these conditions, hospitality leaders may be required to adopt a change-oriented or transformational style of leadership.

6. Suggestions and Recommendations

This review advocates for and even the researchers have stressed the importance of organizational leadership as being fundamental to the success of firms, even more so for industries that are global and dynamic. In order to effectively cope with these conditions, hospitality leaders may be required to adopt a change-oriented or transformational style of leadership. Hence, it may be recommended to the hospitality industry to follow the transformational leadership style by the organizational leaders

and achieve the organizational goals and objectives. There by individual employee development will be there along with the overall organizational development by capturing the pulse of common people and markets of both domestic and globally. Few suggestions are for hospitality industry to capture the vast market by their hospitality and service both nationally and internationally. This will uplift the hospitality industry economically and individual livelihood will be more developed.

There are few recommendations to government authorities to look into the matters of development of hospitality industry and provide them basic infrastructure and work for the betterment of their lives.

References

1. Akhtar, M. N., Long, L., & Nazir, S. (2015). Impact of organizational change antecedents on job satisfaction: The mediating role of perceived fulfillment of psychological contract. *European Scientific Journal, ESJ*, 11(1).
2. Avolio, B. J., Zhu, W., Koh, W., & Bhatia, P. (2004). Transformational leadership and organizational commitment: Mediating role of psychological empowerment and moderating role of structural distance. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 25(8), 951-968.
3. Chathoth, P. K., & Olsen, M. D. (2002). Organisational leadership and strategy in the hospitality industry. *Journal of Services Research*, 2(1), 5.
4. Dutton, J. E., Dukerich, J. M., & Harquail, C. V. (1994). Organizational images and member identification. *Administrative science quarterly*, 239-263.
5. Minett, D., Yaman, H. R., & Denizci, B. (2009). Leadership styles and ethical decision-making in hospitality management. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 28(4), 486-493.
6. Ogbonna, E., & Harris, L. C. (2002). Managing organisational culture: Insights from the hospitality industry. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 12(1), 33-53.
7. Orabi, T. G. A. (2016). The impact of transformational leadership style on organizational performance: Evidence from Jordan. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 6(2), 89-102.
8. Tracey, J. B., & Hinkin, T. R. (1996). How transformational leaders lead in the hospitality industry
9. Wagener, S., Gorgievski, M., & Rijdsdijk, S. (2010). Businessman or host? Individual differences between entrepreneurs and small business owners in the hospitality industry. *The Service Industries Journal*, 30(9), 1513-1527.
10. Yammarino, F. J., Spangler, W. D., & Bass, B. M. (1993). Transformational leadership and performance: A longitudinal investigation. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 4(1), 81-102.
11. <http://searchcio.techtarget.com/definition/organizational-goals>
12. <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/organizational-goals.html>